

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF LANGUAGE AND GENDER

Ergasheva Fazilat Botirovna

Surxondaryo viloyati Uzun tumani

1-sonli umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabining ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10002831>

The intensification of genderology and the emergence of research in this area attract attention by their belonging to the culture of speech and serve as one of the factors of the emergence of research in this area. Because speech and speech culture differ in their differences in male and female gender. In male and female speech, Lison and word utilization also differ in their gender differences and, therefore, in their social status. The position of a man or woman in space and time, their place in the family and society, what profession they are engaged in, their influence and level in society, as well as hakojo circumstances cannot but influence their speech. In addition, it is quite natural that their age characteristics, such as childhood, adolescence, youth, middle age and old age, also leave a mark on the will of Leeson and the word. An elderly person can laugh if he speaks like a teenager and uses elements of the language that a teenager uses in his speech. Therefore, they cannot be brought to uniformity. Adjectives associated with the culture of speech are formed as a result of the influence of space, time, psychological environment, volume of communication, dialect and other objects and are defined as an individual style of speech.

In the theoretical aspect, it is appropriate to note that in the 60-70s of the XX century, as a result of the widespread spread of the women's movement in the West, Linguistics, along with many social sciences, began to enter the field of sciences related to gender studies.[1:2] over time, gender studies in the field of language and communication have increasingly attracted the attention of researchers. An independent scientific direction has been formed in Russian linguistics - gender Linguistics, also called linguistic genderology. The first research in this direction was conducted by Yu.I.Goroshko, Yu.A.Zemskaya, A.V.Vakhobov, N.V.Telia, T.B.Kryuchkova, A.V.Made by Kirilina and others.

As already mentioned, the study of how gender, as well as various factors influence the choice of language means, has become a new area of research in linguistics. In our opinion, when a certain system of gender identity is revealed in the formation of speech culture through gender-based speech research, linguoculturology is enriched and improved.

In place of the shpu, there is a need to step back a little and give an interpretation of the concept of "gender". Initially, this term was used in history, historiography, sociology and psychology, and then it was adopted into linguistics. Scientists have discovered that a person has two different sexes: biological sex and socio-cultural sex. Biological sex is a set of anatomical, physiological, biochemical and genetic features that distinguish a male body from a female one in order to distinguish a man from a woman. As for the concept of gender, there is still no single view of gender nature in science. The word itself does not have sufficient translation even into Uzbek. Its spelling and pronunciation are borrowed from English. Therefore, it is important to understand the meaning and meaning of the word "gender" in English. V.K. In the English-Russian dictionary of Muller, the concept of gender has two meanings: the first is "grammatical gender", and the second is the game sign "gender", [2] is explained as. T.de Lorette gives a short tour of the meaning of the category "gender" in dictionaries of different countries. In the Dictionary of the English Language (The American

Heritage Dictionary of English Language), the word "gender" is defined primarily as a classification term that includes a morphological feature ("grammatical gender"). This dictionary explains that another meaning of the word "gender" is "gender classification; gender" [3]. The Dictionary of American Heritage English explains that another meaning of gender is "representative". Thus, gender is not a social relation of biological sex, but a manifestation of each person from the point of view of specific social relations. T.de according to Loreti, the gender system is a system of representations that imposes values (identity, prestige, status in the social hierarchy)to people in society, as well as a socio-cultural construct, as well as a semiotic tool" [4:3] therefore, the gender factor can also influence a person's speech, determining the state of the level of cultural discourse in his interpersonal communication. It can also be added that the judgment that the same gender is at the same age or that they live in the same space and time leads to the fact that their speech culture remains the same is also incorrect. There is no denying the differences in the speech of a woman breathing in rural areas, in the use of cultural speech - with the woman she finds on the street in the city-in an environment where information is widely distributed. The same can be said about men. After all, in sexual culture, gender becomes normative, closely related to the biological and anatomical features of a person. Accordingly, gender hierarchy and gender behavior are not determined by nature, but are "constructed" by society, determined by social control and cultural traditions and institutions. It would also be appropriate to consider gender relations as an important aspect of social organization, especially expressing its systemic features and structuring relations between speech subjects. At the same time, gender relations are defined in language in the form of culturally conditioned stereotypes that leave a trace in the behavior of an individual, including in his speech, and in the processes of his linguistic socialization.

Speech by its nature is considered not only anthropocentric, but also androcentric, that is, first of all, the one that reflects the male appearance of the world. A.V.As Kirilina notes: "Androcentrism, inherent in all languages functioning in Christian and Muslim cultures, manifests itself in different languages with varying degrees of intensity, therefore, in poetics it is necessary to take into account literary work, gender and tactics." When considering the grammatical point of view of the appearance of jargons in male and female speech, it was noticed that nouns, verbs, numerals and adverbs from independent categories of words, exclamation words from separate groups of words are more often used in male speech. In addition, it was found that monosyllabic simple sentences, incomplete sentences, imperative sentences, partial subordinate clauses are often used in male speech culture. These sentences also involve polysemous words, labels, onomimes, synonyms, and some manifestations of limited vocabulary. And in women's speech culture, pronouns, verbs, prepositions are mainly involved. From a syntactic point of view, adaptive and related conjunctions, simple compound sentences, subordinate clauses, some types of monosyllabic sentences, union fragmentary sentences, isolated annotated fragmentary sentences, emotionally excited sentences, partial command sentences, exclamation sentences are involved. Different gender levels of the text of works of art are visible in the linguistic, stylistic analysis of male and female speech. When considered in this aspect, the perception of the culture of written speech in works of art gives clarity in many cases.

Conclusion

In general, the term "gender" was used to describe the social, cultural and psychological aspects of "men" versus "women", that is, people in society, specific and important characteristics, stereotypes and roles that determine the position of women and men.

References:

1. Grigoryan A.A. The state and perspective of gender linguistics in the West at the end of the XX—beginning of the XXI centuries: Abstract. Dis... cand. go. sciences'. - Volgograd.: IGU, 2005. -
2. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n7kommunikativno-pragmaticheskie-aspekty-proyavleniya-ekspressivnosti-v-muzhskih-i-zhenskih-korotkih-elektronnyh-soobscheniyah>
3. <https://en-academic.com/dic.nsf/enwiki/>
4. Grigoryan A.A. The state and perspective of gender linguistics in the West at the end of the XX—beginning of the XXI centuries: Abstract. Dis... cand. go. sciences'. - Volgograd.: IGU, 2005. -
5. Textbook on the course "Fundamentals of gender studies " by I.Chkalov. - M.: MTSGI, 2000.
6. Grigoryan A.A. The state and perspective of gender linguistics in the West at the end of the XX—beginning of the XXI centuries: Abstract. Dis... cand. go. sciences'. - Volgograd.: IGU, 2005.